

**Report on definitions and database setup for the Wind
Atlas
Deliverable D4.5**

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Executive Summary

This report describes the fields and quantities that are to be served by the NEWA. It divides these into two parts, fields given at microscale and fields given at mesoscale. Tables describe in what heights the fields are given and whether the data are time mean or time varying. Because predictability is one of the newer fields to be presented by NEWA the methodologies used and quantities given are described in some detail. The report also outlines considerations given to data flow and data processing. Data handling issues are inherent within the model chain used in the wind atlas, and will be part of subsequent processing of the huge modelling datasets for the future.

1 Introduction

This document outlines two important elements of the New European Wind Atlas:

- i) the definition of the quantities to be served by that atlas and
- ii) the manner in which the data can be organized in the atlas.

The first element has been largely influenced by the D4.1 “Report on Definition of wind atlas output parameters”. This report described the results of an end-user questionnaire about desired fields and quantities to feature in the atlas.

The second element concerning the manner in which the data is organized has been developed through discussion amongst project partners and institutions that have needed to address the issue of storage and application of large quantities of data. These issues are addressed within the discipline of data engineering and big data. This report touches on suitable Hadoop approach for the atlas.

2 Definitions

The definition of fields and quantities to be served is broken into two parts. Those belonging to the microscale outputs with a suggested horizontal grid spacing of 50 m, and those belonging to the mesoscale outputs with a suggested horizontal grid spacing of 3 km.

The nomenclature justed in this section will use **Field** to refer to a particular property of interest. Each **Field** can then have several **Quantities** associated to it, for example, climate mean, or sectorwise mean, time series, and so on.

The fields to be given for the microscale outputs are shown in Table 1. It can be seen that the fields are given as long term mean quantities only. It can also be seen that the fields are given over three heights, except for quantities pertaining to the surface layer.

Table 1: Table showing the microscale fields and quantities to be served by NEWA.

Field	Quantity	Heights [m]
Power density	Climate mean	50, 100, 200
	Sectorwise mean (not weighted)	50, 100, 200
Horizontal winds	Climate mean wind speed	50, 100, 200
	Sectorwise wind speed frequency distribution	50, 100, 200
	Sector frequency distribution (wind rose)	50, 100, 200
	Maps of Weibull parameters	50,100,200
Roughness length	Long term mean value	Surface
Surface elevation	Long term mean value	Surface

The fields to be given for the mesoscale outputs are shown in

Table 2. It can be seen that the fields are given as long term mean quantities and also time series. The time series are composed of 30-minute and 1-monthly means of the fields. It can also be seen that the fields are given over a large range of heights, except for quantities pertaining to the surface layer.

Table 2: Table showing the mesoscale fields and quantities to be served by NEWA.

Field	Quantity	Interval	Heights [m]
Power density	Climate mean	Static	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
	Sectorwise mean (not weighted)	Static	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
Horizontal winds	Long-term mean wind speed	Static	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
	Sectorwise wind speed frequency distribution	Static	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
	Sector frequency distribution (wind rose)	Static	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
	Wind speed time series	30-min & 1-monthly	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
	Seasonal Variability	Static	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
	Daily Variability	Static	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
	Wind direction time series	30-min & 1-monthly	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
Roughness length	Long-term mean value		Surface
Surface elevation	Long-term mean value		Surface
Friction velocity	Time series	30-min & 1-monthly	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
Air temperature	Long-term mean	Static	2,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
	Time series	30-min & 1-monthly	2,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
Air density	Long-term mean	Static	Surface
	Time series	30-min & 1-monthly	Surface
Turbulence intensity (TKE as proxy)	Long-term mean	Static	50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
	Time series	30-min & 1-monthly	50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
Relative humidity	Long-term mean	Static	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500

	Time series	30-min & 1-monthly	10,50,75,100,150,200,250, 500
Inverse M-O length	Long-term mean	Static	Surface layer
	Time series	30-min & 1-monthly	Surface layer
Boundary layer height	Long-term mean	Static	-
Sea / near-surface temperature	Time series	30-min & 1-monthly	-
Time series parameters	Min, max, std. dev. of time series parameters	Static	50,75,100,150,200,250, 500 or surface as appropriate
	Ensemble mean	Static	50,75,100,150,200,250, 500 or surface as appropriate
	Ensemble spread	Static	50,75,100,150,200,250, 500 or surface as appropriate
Predictability	Predictability	Monthly	11,18,25,32 days and 1,2,3 months
Icing	Long-term probability	Static	50,75,100,150,200,250, 500

2.1 Predictability of sub-seasonal to seasonal climate predictions

The New European Wind Atlas will integrate for the first time a skill assessment of sub-seasonal to seasonal climate predictions. The aim is to provide a clear description of the predictability of climate predictions at different time scales assessing the evolution of this predictability in different European regions. The main objective is to help decision makers to answer the question: What can they expect on the use of wind forecast at different time horizons? How predictable is the wind resource at the site of interest?

Sub-seasonal to seasonal climate predictions fill the gap between medium-range weather forecasting and decadal climate predictions. In those predictions, the atmospheric system has lost most of its memory from the initial conditions. As a consequence, predicting hourly variations after 5-6 days does not make any sense. However, there is opportunity for skillful predictions over longer time-averaging windows, for example by taking a weekly, monthly and seasonal time averages.

For a specific variable, e.g. wind speed, predictability will depend on the region, the season, the windows forecast and the teleconnections with the main sources of predictability. For sub-seasonal climate predictions the main sources of predictability come from the Madden-Julian Oscillation or MJO, the stratospheric-troposphere interactions, the land/ice/snow initial conditions, the ENSO and NAO teleconnections, blocking conditions, local SST anomalies and soil moisture anomalies. The El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) is the most important source of predictability at seasonal timescales.

Taking these characteristics into account, a detailed description of the metrics and the implementation into the Atlas is shown below.

2.2 Metrics

Rather than coming up with complex estimates of different characteristics of forecast skill and reliability whose relevance strongly depends on the specific applications, Fair Ranked Probability Skill Score (FairRPSS) will be used. Fair-RPSS is a measure of the predictive skill for the probabilistic forecasts for categorical events. The Fair-RPSS has been computed based on categorical forecasts for terciles (Figure 1). Three equi-probable events associated with the two terciles of the climatological distribution of the reference: wind speed exceeding the upper tercile, not exceeding the lower tercile and between the two terciles.

Scores below zero indicate that the predictions are unskillful, those equal to zero are equal to the climatology forecasts, and anything above zero is an improvement upon climatology, up to 1, which indicates a 'perfect' forecast.

Figure 1: Upper panel: ECMWF System 4 near-surface wind speed probabilistic forecast of most likely tercile category, for December-January-February 2016/2017. The seasonal predictions have been issued the 1st of November. The most likely category (below normal, normal, and above normal) and its percentage of probability to occur is shown. White colour indicates that the forecast probabilities are below 40% for all 3 categories. Bottom panel: grey colour has been used to mask those regions where Ranked Probability Skill Score is below 0.

2.3 Database set up

During the project, the main source of climate data is a collection of model outputs and reanalysis. For model outputs, the data used will be from different meteorological centers that provide climate predictions. The data is downloaded in their native format (grib for ECMWF, netCDF for the other ones). The reanalysis data is downloaded in their original grib format and processed afterwards.

The data collection method consist in ssh connections to the remote data servers and retrievals through ftp or the webapi from the ECMWF. During the project, from the “raw/original” data some statistics and tailored products have been created. This data mainly consist in netCDF files.

2.4 Web set up

The wind atlas will provide an objective characterization of forecast skill in an easy interpretive and user-friendly manner for an end user to allow application of the predictions at sub-seasonal to seasonal timescales in a decision-making process. The information will be provided in a map. Each grid cell (1° and $1,5^\circ$ for seasonal and sub-seasonal respectively) will show forecast skill pattern for a specific system (e.g. ECMWF-S4), month (e.g. January) and forecast window (e.g. monthly averages with 1 month lead time). Selecting a region will open a panel with complete assessment of the forecast skill. A mock-up version of the detail panel is shown in Figure 2.

FairRPSS of ECMWF 10-m wind speed for 1996-2015 over Europe

Figure 2: Mock-up version of the detail panel to be displayed for each region.

3 Wind Atlas data flow

In the following section aspects of the data and database setup will be outlined.

Figure 3 shows a schematic diagram for how modelling and data are linked in a series of data stages and processes. The start of this flow is the raw mesoscale output from WRF. To reduce the amount of data only relevant levels and quantities are retained for further processing. Tabulation or reformatting gives either times series datasets or distribution datasets for subsequent processing. The distribution datasets are used in the generalization processing in order to be used in subsequent microscale modelling, or are used for mapping of the mesoscale fields of interest. Microscale modelling and map processing are the final parts of the data flow, yielding the microscale fields of interests.

Wind Atlas data flow

Figure 3: Schematic showing the data flow from raw mesoscale modelling output to mesoscale and microscale maps layers, via a number of processes. Data stages are shown with orange boxes and processes are shown with green boxes.

4 Database setup

As outlined in the previous section the wind atlas will offer provision of distributions and statistics and provision of time series. Ideally the modelling datasets should be available for advanced analysis of model data such as, but not limited to, searches for:

- abrupt changes in wind conditions (space and time)
- shear and veer conditions
- low level jets
- spatial gradients

In addition the database of modelling data should be capable of fast post-processing, for instance, to offer calculation of capacity factor calculation for specific power curves.

Such requirements place demands on the performance of the database system. Typically within the discipline of mesoscale meteorology, the model outputs are stored as 2-d or 3-d spatial fields of specific quantities at given time, called time slices.

If the quantity Q is stored in an 3-d array $q(x,y,t)$ contiguous in x and then y (Figure 5) then to extract a time slice out of this array can be very quick to give $q(x,y,t=t_n)$. In actual practice of the example of the time slice shown in Figure 4 it can take around ~ 0.01 seconds to produce a single time slice. However, to extract a time series from the same 3-d array for a single point, i.e. $q(x=x_i, y=y_j, t)$, can take around ~ 200 seconds.

Figure 4: Example of a stack of map slices

Figure 5: Data array set up in a contiguous arrangement.

Figure 6: Data array set up in a chunked arrangement.

If instead the data is arranged in a chunked array (Figure 6) then the difference in performance of extracting time series and time slices can be evened out. So in actual practice of the same data given before, using a chunked array of the extraction of a time slice and the extraction of a time series both take around ~1 second.

However the choices surrounding chunking dimensions should be considered carefully. If the chunks are too small there is a large overhead in finding the appropriate chunks where the needed data is residing. The Hierarchical Data Format 5 (HDF5) supports chunked layouts. HDF5 is a data model, library, and file format for storing and managing data. The later version of the well-known netCDF format, much used in meteorology, uses HDF5 from netCDF-4.

One example of a post-process that might be considered for the wind atlas is the calculation of capacity factor. To evaluate capacity factor a summation $\sum f(u) P(u)$ is performed, where $P(u)$ is the normalized power curve with a value ranging from 0 to 1 and $f(u)$ the wind speed frequency distribution, described by a Weibull distribution with parameters A and k . In the wind atlas the parameters A and k vary in 4 dimensions $A(x,y,z,d)$ and $k(x,y,z,d)$, with x, y, z in space and, d , wind direction sector. In the wind atlas we can expect the total size of A or k array to be of order 10 billion.

With such large arrays, the more conventional way of processing by loading data to a computer node becomes difficult to manage. Instead the paradigm is changed to one in which the processing moves to the data. This can be achieved with Hadoop (Figure 7). Hadoop not only allows for processing to move to the data, it also allows for the processing to be distributed over a number of nodes in a cluster. If a 1TB file needs to be processed, it might take 60 minutes on a single computer node, but with Hadoop and 10 computer nodes, it might only take 6 minutes. More information on Hadoop can be found at <https://www.thinkbiganalytics.com/>.

Figure 7: Schematic showing a Hadoop set up for distributing data and processing.

Hadoop uses the Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS). HDFS allows large files to be broken into blocks and spread across nodes in a cluster (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Schematic of HDFS, (left) the original data file is split into blocks and (right) distributed over a number of data nodes.

An important element of Hadoop is MapReduce. MapReduce is the way that a calculation is broken down and organized over the distributed data, Figure 9. The **Mapper** functions organize blocks of data in a way that allows the data to be aggregated. The **Reducer** functions apply any kind of aggregate logic. Taking the case of the capacity factor calculation as an example,

$$CF(i, j) = \sum_{k=1}^N f(i, j, k) P(k)$$

Map function produces an "intermediate" result ahead of an aggregation process:

- emit = (**key**, **value**) in general
- emit = ((i,j), ($f(i, j, k) P(k)$)) in the Capacity Factor case
- The **key** is the location (i,j)
- The **value** is the CF "component" of each wind speed (u(k)) at (i,j).

Reduce function produces the final result by doing an aggregation, in this case the summation for the capacity factor:

- **key** (i,j)
- **value** = $\sum_{k=1}^N f(i, j, k) P(k)$
- The result is the capacity factor for location (i,j)

Figure 9: schematic of the MapReduce, the map function prepares an intermediate result from the blocks of data, the reduce function aggregates the intermediate results.

5 Summary

This report has first outlined the fields and quantities that are to be served by the NEWA. It divides these into two parts, fields given at microscale and fields given at mesoscale. Tables describe in what heights the fields are given and whether the data are time mean or time varying. Because predictability is one of the newer fields to be presented by NEWA the methodologies used and quantities given are described in some detail.

Second, the report outlines consideration given to data flow and data processing. Close attention to this is necessary due to the very large amounts of data to be produced and processed. Part of this is inherent within the model chain used in the wind atlas, and part can be used for subsequent processing of the huge modelling datasets

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